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Corso di Laurea Triennale in

Economia e commercio

**Supply Chain Management: The Role of Optimization and AI
in Exploring New Horizons**

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Anno Accademico 2024/2025

Abstract

Supply Chain Management (SCM) is one of the most important drivers of organizational performance with its contribution to customer satisfaction, operational effectiveness, and competitiveness. This thesis aims to explore the evolving SCM environment with specific focus on the value-added role of new technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoT), Big Data Analytics, Blockchain, and Robotics.

The first chapter provides a foundational understanding of SCM. Dealing with its growth, its importance, and the impact of poor management.

The second chapter elaborates on how optimization techniques are enhancing supply chain performance. These optimization techniques vary from fuzzy logic in supplier assessment and IoT-based applications to the importance of big data analytics for the decision-making process and the key role of blockchain in securing the supply chain.

The third chapter starts exploring the enormous impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI), specifying that the relationship between AI and SCM is long-standing but drawing attention to the fact that the disruptive evolution of AI in recent years is a total revolution. This chapter continues with the analysis of how AI is reshaping global shipment and logistics, including a case study on AI's role in Maersk's shipping and supply chain, and concludes by elaborating on how AI is strengthening the food supply chain, including a case study on the IBM Food Trust and Walmart's AI-driven supply chain.

Finally, the fourth chapter delves into what will be the future of SCM, exposing that the revolution of SCM 4.0 is not yet concluded, treating the importance of the rise of green and ethical supply chains and the future of logistics through robotics.

Contents

Abstract.....	2
1. Why supply chain management is so important.....	5
1.1 Understanding the supply chain.....	5
1.1.1 Diverse perspectives on supply chain management.....	6
1.2 Definition and scope of supply chain management.....	8
1.3 SCM as a driver of customer satisfaction and competitive advantage	11
1.4 The consequences of poor supply chain management.....	13
2. How is it possible to optimize the supply chain.....	16
2.1 Optimizing using fuzzy approach.....	16
2.1.1 Fuzzy Logic in supplier evaluation and selection.....	16
2.1.2 Fuzzy Models for Supply Chain Aggregate Production Planning (SCAPP) .	17
2.1.3 Fuzzy-Based resource allocation and logistics optimization	18
2.2 IoT-based supply chain management.....	19
2.2.1 How IoT is transforming supply chains: top 10 applications for efficiency and security.....	20
2.2.2 IoT and the evolution of supply chain management: benefits, risks, and future prospects.....	22
2.3 Big data analytics for decision-making in SCM.....	24
2.4 Secure supply chain management with blockchain.....	27
2.4.1 What is the blockchain.....	28
2.4.2 How the supply chain is being revolutionized by blockchain technology.....	28
3. Artificial Intelligence in supply chain management.....	31
3.1 A long-standing relationship.....	31
3.2 The enormous impact of the last few years.....	33
3.2.1 Rethinking supply chains with Artificial Intelligence.....	34
3.2.2 AI under pressure during the COVID-19 crisis.....	36
3.3 Sailing into the future: how AI is reshaping global shipment and logistics.....	37
3.3.1 Case Study: AI's role in Maersk's shipping and supply chain.....	40
3.4 Artificial intelligence in the food supply chain from automation to ethics.....	43
3.4.1 Case Study: IBM Food Trust & Walmart's AI-driven supply chain.....	47
4. The future of supply chain management.....	50
4.1 The incomplete revolution of SCM 4.0.....	50
4.2 Sustainability in SCM: the rise of green and ethical supply chains.....	52
4.3 Robotics in supply chain: automation and the future of logistics.....	56

Conclusion.....	59
Bibliography.....	60

1. Why supply chain management is so important

1.1 Understanding the supply chain

The endeavour to articulate a comprehensive definition of the concept commonly referred to as the supply chain is inherently intricate, as its importance and implications can be understood and analysed from a multitude of perspectives and interpretations.

Nevertheless, it is a widely held consensus among economists that the concept of a supply chain can be comprehensively characterized as a cohesive and interconnected process in which a diverse array of business entities collaborate synergistically with the primary objective of: (1) procuring essential raw materials that serve as the foundational inputs for production, (2) transforming these acquired raw materials through various manufacturing processes into designated final products that meet specific market demands, and (3) ensuring the efficient distribution and delivery of these completed final products to retailers, thereby facilitating their availability to end consumers.

The supply chain is one of the few economic processes that affects all internal phases of a firm, from commercial relationships with suppliers to post-sales services. It is obvious that a business without a strong supply chain would fail.

A common mistake in understanding supply chains is assuming they operate in a strictly unidirectional manner. This perspective greatly oversimplifies what is actually a much more dynamic and interconnected system.

To illustrate this, imagine placing a necklace on a table. At first sight, not to say under closer review, it's very hard to say where it starts and where it ends because every link connects one to the next. The supply chain works fairly the same. Conventionally, it has been viewed from left to right, starting from suppliers, then production, followed by distribution, until the final destination: the customer. However, this isn't the full picture. If we shift our perspective and look at the supply chain from right to left, we see the crucial role of backward information flow from the customer right into the supply, meaning back-up corresponding to feedback and data qualities. This standing-down information flow assists a business in upgrading its dependent procedures as required towards enhancing optimisation, thus towards improving innovation in general. It's incorrect to think that customer preferences, market trends, and performance feedback don't just stop at the point of sale; they travel upstream, influencing manufacturers, distributors, and even suppliers.

The left-to-right flow and the right-to-left one are cleverly shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Supply chain (example)

Source: Stadler, 2005

1.1.1 Diverse perspectives on supply chain management

At the beginning of this paragraph, by introducing the notion of supply chain, I mentioned the existence of various perspectives in which it can be seen.

According to “A Research Note on Defining the Concept of Supply Chain” by Zouaghi, Laghouag (2011).

Exist mainly five perspectives of approaching the concept of supply chain:

- Functional and process oriented.
- Strategic.
- Systemic.
- Structural and network oriented.
- Relational.

The functional and process-oriented perspective views the supply chain as a series of linked functions, activities, and processes to serve customers' needs. Ayers (2006) describes it as a network of physical, informational, financial, and knowledge flows designed to deliver products and services via linked suppliers. Beamon (1998) emphasises its integrated character, highlighting the forward movement of materials and the reverse movement of information. Similarly, Quinn (1997) and Zhang et al. (2003) also define it

as a network of procurement, production, distribution, and consumption processes. Scholars like Monczka et al. (2010) and Arshinder et al. (2008) stress the importance of consistency in coordinating these activities to enhance coordination. Essentially, this view places the supply chain as an integrated system of functions, operations, and activities that facilitate product and service delivery effectively.

The strategic perspective of the supply chain considers it as a source of competitive value and value creation. Porter (1985, 2008) initially developed the concept of the "value system," which extends beyond a company's internal value chain to include suppliers, channels, and customers. Bertazzoli et al. (2011) note that aggregate value created is dependent on market conditions, supplier relationships, and industry policy. Lambert and Cooper (2000) argue that supply chains need to be strategically aligned for optimal value creation. Lee (2010) focuses on process reinvention, cost leadership, and strategic partnerships for competitiveness. Ketchen et al. (2008) view supply chains as strategic assets that maximise speed, cost, quality, and flexibility. Such an understanding positions the supply chain as an active system integrating different enterprises for maximising customer value and differentiation in competition.

The systemic perspective conceives the supply chain as an interdependent system comprising material, technology, human, and organizational elements that transform inputs into outputs. Stevens (1989) describes it as a network of suppliers, factories, distribution points, and buyers connected by material and information flows. Saikouk et al. (2012) envision supply chains as dynamic systems in which autonomous firms collaborate towards common goals. Ketchen et al. (2008) and Leukel and Kirn (2008) concur with this evaluation by defining supply chains as networks of production, transformation, and distribution. This acknowledges the uncertainty and complexity that arise in supply chains, focusing especially on reducing disruptions and facilitating seamless operations through interconnected networks.

The structural and network perspective perceives the supply chain as an interorganisational network that is linked by numerous types of relationships. Borgatti and Foster (2003) refer to its structural nature, while Miles and Snow (1992) state that it is usually controlled by a focal company that is in charge of the suppliers and buyers. Sanders (2012) sets up the supply chain as a network involving sourcing, manufacturing, warehouse administration, order tracking, and distribution. Swaminathan et al. (1998) and Santoso et al. (2005) explain it as a collection of autonomous entities that acquire, produce, and distribute. Ganeshan and Harrison (1995) point out its occurrence in

manufacturing as well as service industries. Lastly, this viewpoint is interested in supply chain structure, enumerating the entities and their connections.

The relational perspective places the supply chain in the form of a network of relationships among key stakeholders. It is described by Beamon (1998) as an inter-system of supplier-manufacturer-distributor-retailer relations. Mukhtar and Shaharoun (2002) state that supply chains can only be explained by looking at the nature of the relationships. Ketchen and Giunipero (2004) describe supply chain organisations as cooperative long-term alliances that share their resources to achieve common goals. This theory, in contrast to the network perspective, does emphasise both rational and social factors in relationships to value their role towards supply chain effectiveness and performance.

1.2 Definition and scope of supply chain management

After completely understanding what a supply chain is and how it may be viewed, it is clear why managing the supply chain is so crucial.

Before we begin to explain what supply chain management is and what its scope is, it is important to understand how supply chain management and logistics management relate to each other.

The first thing we should do is define logistics. In a supply chain, logistics describes the movement and storage of components, resources, and finished goods. Inbound and outbound procedures to and from warehouses, as well as internal and external material handling and transportation activities, are all included in logistics. It also covers the provision of services and information sharing amongst the many supply chain phases.

Now that we understand what logistics and supply chains are. We are able to define logistics management and supply chain management:

“Supply chain management encompasses the planning and management of all supply chain operations. Importantly, it also includes the coordination and collaboration with channel partners, which can be suppliers, intermediaries, third party service providers, and customers. In essence, supply chain management integrates supply and demand management within and across companies.” (Zijm & Klumpp & Heragu & Regattieri, 2019).

“Logistics management is that part of supply chain management that plans, implements, and controls the efficient, effective forward and reverse flow and storage of goods,

services and related information between the point of origin and the point of consumption in order to meet customers' requirements. It typically includes inbound and outbound transportation management, fleet management, warehousing, materials handling, order fulfilment, logistics network design, inventory management, supply/demand planning, and management of third-party logistics services providers." (Zijm & Klumpp & Heragu & Regattieri, 2019).

Logistics is still often considered synonymous with transport in many popular magazines and in the public mind. The definitions above clearly indicate a much broader scope of logistics, but to avoid any confusion, Figure 2 shows with clarity the hierarchy between supply chain management, logistics management and transport operations.

Figure 2: hierarchy of SCM, logistics management and transport

Source: Henk Zijm, Matthias Klumpp, Alberto Regattieri, Sunderesh Heragu: *Operations, Logistics and Supply Chain Management* (Springer, 2019)

Having created the framework for a conscientious knowledge of SCM, we proceed with the understanding of the fundamental purpose, the difficulty, and the advantages of well-managed supply chain management.

The main objective of supply chain management (SCM) is to act as a strategic instrument for achieving a long-term competitive advantage. This is mainly achieved through minimisation of costs and the achievement of high customer satisfaction levels (Mentzer et al., 2001). Moreover, a successful SCM strategy demands that organisations evaluate environmental issues, recognise possible constraints, and institute relevant interventions to sustain competitive performance (Fawcett et al., 2008). A key part of this process is the utilisation of supply chain partners' (SCPs) knowledge, experience, and capabilities, which together create a competitive network (Mentzer et al., 2001).

Implementing an integrated SCM strategy is faced with numerous challenges. Fawcett et al. (2008) classified these barriers into two broad categories: inter-firm rivalry and managerial complexity. The most significant inter-firm rivalry barriers include internal and external conflict, inadequate SCM planning, lack of strategic vision, low trust among partners, low executive commitment, and low SCM knowledge. Among them, internal and external conflicts are the most dangerous, as they can completely derail supply chain activities in a very short time. Poor planning and a lack of long-term vision can have a delayed impact but can ultimately lead to dramatic failures.

Conversely, managerial complexity involves discordant supply chain processes, structural aberrations, and corporate culture differences between supply chain partners (Fawcett et al., 2008). In this respect, the major barriers encompass information systems and information technology (IS/IT) deficiencies, inflexible organisational structures, poor performance measures, and lack of well-defined partnership procedures. Importantly, IS/IT deficiencies are especially harmful as they can lead to extensive loss of competitive edge.

To overcome these barriers, Fawcett et al. (2008) identified several strategic solutions such as increased information visibility, cross-firm and cross-functional collaboration, collaborative planning implementation, IT infrastructure strengthening, implementation of a proper SCM vision, and emphasising human issues. Other effective mechanisms are supplier certification programs, customer segmentation, and common investment schemes.

The advantages of a properly managed supply chain management (SCM) system are numerous. Fawcett et al. (2008) demonstrate that the most important benefits are greater inventory turnover, higher revenues, lower SCM expenditures, greater product availability, lower order cycle times, greater responsiveness, improved capital utilisation, and lower logistics expenses.

A streamlined supply chain is the key to optimum cost savings in various operations like information exchange, manufacturing, warehousing, transportation, and financing. Rising capital costs, real estate charges, and freight rates¹ further justify the importance of proper SCM (Koch, 2006). Proper planning in material purchasing, production planning, and distribution minimizes inventory holding, decreases cost, and eliminates wastage of time and effort (Verma et al., 2006). In addition, successful SCM can have a significant impact

¹ Freight rates: Cost charged for transporting goods, determined by factors like distance, cargo type, and market conditions.

on inventory investment across industries, buffering the effects of economic volatility (Heng et al., 2005).

1.3 SCM as a driver of customer satisfaction and competitive advantage

Supply Chain Management (SCM) has a significant influence on customer satisfaction because it, in a direct way, determines the availability and delivery of the products, understanding of the costs, and consistency of the services provided. An efficient supply chain guarantees that the customer gets the product they want in the shortest time and of the quality they like most. For this reason, inefficiencies in the supply chain translate into delays, shortages, excessive costs, and poor service, which all have negative effects on the customer experience.

With today's competitive market that includes the growing expectations of customers, organisations have no other option than to make supply chain efficiency their top priority in their strategic agendas. With this, they can enjoy customer satisfaction and loyalty over the long term.

Effective SCM enables the anticipation and satisfaction of customer needs through efficient coordination between suppliers, manufacturers, distributors and retailers. Adoption of practices like "Efficient Consumer Response" (ECR) is one of the most important ways to achieve that kind of effectiveness.

The ECR strategy has its roots in the early 1990s, but it found relevance only in 1999 and 2000, thanks principally to Joyce M. Hoffman and Satish Mehra with their "Efficient consumer response as a supply chain strategy for grocery businesses".

ECR is a supply chain strategy developed in the grocery industry for achieving maximum responsiveness to consumers' needs and, simultaneously, minimum unnecessary inventory and operational costs. The ECR strategy is designed to minimize the complexity of the supply chain by enhancing collaboration between manufacturers, distributors, and retailers to make product flow sensitive to real-time demand by consumers.

Hoffman and Mehra (2000) describe Efficient Consumer Response (ECR) as a strategic approach that acts as a "natural pull," utilising point-of-sale (POS) information to trigger replenishment orders according to actual demand. This strategy is aimed at dealing with all sorts of inefficiencies typically seen in traditional supply chains that rely extensively on forecasts disassociated from real consumer behaviours.

Through the collaborative, real-time sharing of supply chain information, ECR minimizes lead times, stockouts, and above-average inventory, which all result in improved customer satisfaction. Further, ECR emphasises collaboration and information sharing so that all the stakeholders in the supply chain can live in harmony to achieve shared objectives. Through sophisticated analysis of data and coordinated planning, companies can foresee changes in consumer trends, modify their manufacturing and delivery plans to meet the same, and design a highly responsive supply chain to meet market needs.

The application of ECR has been seen to make supply chains more productive, resulting in improved product availability at lower cost, both of which are determinants of increased levels of customer satisfaction.

Reliability is a primary determinant of the impact of supply chain performance on customer satisfaction. By consistently delivering complete products in a timely manner, firms develop a reputation for reliability that, in turn, reinforces customer trust and engenders brand loyalty. On the other hand, an unstable supply chain characterised by constant delays, shortages and variable quality of service frustrates and irritates customers.

A well-structured SCM system improves reliability by optimizing inventory management, logistics, and supplier coordination. By leveraging advanced forecasting models and just-in-time (JIT) inventory strategies, businesses can reduce the risk of overstocking or understocking, ensuring that customers always have access to the products they need.

According to ideas included in the research of Hoffman and Mehra (2000), firms that manage their supply chain initiatives, for example, Efficient Consumer Response (ECR), will successfully reduce inventory costs and increase product availability, hence, raise customer satisfaction levels at the same time.

Besides, the ability to respond quickly to unexpected breakdowns, in the form of supplier collapse, transport delays, or abrupt spikes in demand, represents a key factor in maintaining supply chain reliability. Those corporations that invest in improving their supply chains by executing features such as the above-mentioned three, particularly becoming multiple-sourcing, implementing flexible production systems, and also employing a digital supply chain solution that will be the best to deal with the unexpected, thus building customer trust and satisfaction.

The cost-effectiveness within the supply chain has a profound effect on customer satisfaction. By streamlining supply chain operations, organizations can lower logistics, procurement, and inventory management costs. As a result of such cost savings, they can pass them on to customers in the form of competitive pricing, discounts, or value-added services. Conversely, supply chain inefficiencies lead to high operating costs, which often translate into higher prices for offerings.

Hoffman and Mehra (2000) emphasise the need for companies competing in competitive markets, including the grocery industry, to carefully balance the trade-off between cost-cutting and service level to ensure customer satisfaction. Overly aggressive cost-cutting measures that negatively impact the level of service, such as excessively aggressive cuts in inventory or the utilisation of dubious low-cost vendors, lead to negative consequences like stockouts and reduced product quality. The secret to achieving cost-effectiveness along with customer satisfaction is intelligent optimisation of the supply chain with a focus on waste elimination while ensuring high levels of service. Strategies such as lean supply chain management, automation, and artificial intelligence-based forecasting allow organisations to keep costs at a minimum without compromising on reliability, affecting the enterprise and its customers.

SCM is not about moving goods but about delivering value. The companies that will shape the future are those who understand that an efficiently managed supply chain is not some back-office function but a font of customer satisfaction, loyalty, and long-term growth.

1.4 The consequences of poor supply chain management

As already introduced in a company, successful supply chain management enhances operational efficiency, reduces costs, and improves customer satisfaction. It delivers on time, removes inventory waste, and optimises the utilisation of resources. With improved logistics and coordination, companies gain a competitive advantage, improve profitability, and become more resilient to disruption.

But what happens if poor supply chain management is conducted?

Probably the first impacted actors are the consumers, in fact, ineffective management of the supply chain could cause extreme damage to customer satisfaction and thus lead to lost sales, damage to reputations, and reduced brand loyalty.

Although the consumer is at the end of the normally seen supply chain, understood from left to right, they are the most visible and most explicit indicators of supply chain inefficiencies.

The customer usually becomes frustrated whenever delays, stockouts, or inconsistencies in quality happen. Such frustration is translated into negative reviews, reduced trust, and the eventual shift of their preference toward other competitors offering better reliability.

This ineffective management of a supply chain disrupts the effective flow of goods and services by creating unpredictable delivery timelines, inaccurate fulfilment of orders, and lack of availability for products, all of which reduce customer retention rates and the viability of a business in the long run.

Companies that do not invest in robust systems of supply chain risk repeat stockouts, unpredictable delivery patterns, and product quality issues, all of which spell frustration for customers. In this regard, Hoffman and Mehra (2000) point out that these reactive, rather than proactive, approaches to supply chain management lead to companies falling behind consumer demand. Furthermore, mismanaged logistics cause high operational expenses, which are passed on to the clients in the disguise of high prices or poor service. Any interruption in the workflow of a supply chain may result in customers leaving to go to other industry players who can guarantee faultless service delivery, especially in such a price-sensitive sector as retail and grocery.

However, the negative consequences of ineffective supply chain management extend far beyond the consumer.

Inadequacies of poor supply chain management invariably lead to sufficient distortion in the information flow that it could bring about innumerable severe inefficient operations affecting both production processes and inventory-control mechanisms.

The bullwhip effect describes when orders placed with suppliers are more variable than sales made by buyers, indicating a demand distortion; moreover, this distortion is often amplified upstream through the supply chain as it propagates, leading to an amplification of variance and exacerbating problems (Lee & Padmanabhan & Whang, 1997). It creates an environment for manufacturers and suppliers to contend with variable and frequently inflated demand signals, leading to higher operational expenses and affecting scheduling efficiency, in addition to significantly influencing cost-service reliability.

The consequences of these distortions are often very important and capable of influencing operational levels at various tiers. The manufacturer incurs excess raw

materials costs due to unplanned purchases of supplies. Moreover, extra production costs arise from sustaining surplus capacity, inefficient resource usage leads to increased overtime production, and warehousing expenses rise alongside additional transportation costs due to external scheduling and the need for high quality to address demand fluctuations.

Studies suggest that these inefficiencies can lead to excess costs ranging between 12.5% and 25%, significantly impacting financial performance (Kurt Salmon Associates 1993).

Inventory mismanagement is probably the most important problem that any organisation would have to come to terms with and has far-reaching implications. In supply chain provision, many functions involve various actors and stakeholders. Several occasions could lead to a build-up of unnecessary stock stuck in operational processes due to the choices of many different actors who have not communicated properly with each other. Their pressurised work constrains essential working capital and increases storage costs to potentially unsustainable levels. This, as we have already seen, can have a significant effect on the level of service that could reduce customer satisfaction and loyalty, thus affecting the brand image damage landscape in the long run.

Furthermore, companies that work primarily with the latest order information, without contextualising the entire picture of end consumers' demand behaviour, risk failing to plan the management of their valuable resources efficiently. It is undoubtedly accepted behaviour by retailers to use demand realisations as a signal or forecast for future demand, often triggering overreaction in procurement and replenishment, magnifying the already-too-often-wide fluctuations in demand.

To mitigate these issues, improving information sharing, reducing lead times, and aligning supply chain forecasting models with actual sales data are essential steps. Without these measures, poor supply chain management continues to create financial strain, operational inefficiencies, and lost customer trust.

2. How is it possible to optimize the supply chain

2.1 Optimizing using fuzzy approach

All activities in SCM, such as supplier selection, inventory management, etc., entail decision-making. Complexity in the objects evaluated and the cognitive limitations of individuals, most often, make the decision information provided by the managers fuzzy, hence creating a tough decision-making situation.

In the realm of supply chains, the coordination between manufacturers and their suppliers represents a critical and challenging link within the distribution channel.

Numerous models have been conceived for supplier selection decisions, which are often predicated on rather reductionist interpretations of the decision-making process (Boer et al., 1998; Lee et al., 2001). A significant portion of these methodologies appears to overlook the intricate and unstructured characteristics as well as the contextual factors inherent in many contemporary purchasing decisions (Boer et al., 1998).

The fuzzy approach to supply chain management optimization offers a robust solution with the application of linguistic variables and fuzzy logic to enhance decision-making in uncertain environments. By integrating fuzzy set theory with supply chain models, companies can develop more adaptable and robust strategies that enhance efficiency, reduce costs, and improve overall performance.

The following paragraphs will discuss:

- Fuzzy logic in supplier evaluation and selection.
- Fuzzy models for aggregate production planning (SCAPP).
- Fuzzy-based resource allocation and logistics optimization.

2.1.1 Fuzzy Logic in supplier evaluation and selection

One of the most critical areas in which fuzzy logic improves supply chain management is through the selection and evaluation of suppliers. Supplier selection is a multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) problem in which firms consider numerous qualitative and quantitative criteria such as cost, quality, delivery history, flexibility, and reliability. Since the performance of suppliers is typically under uncertainty and the expert's judgement, fuzzy logic provides a superior method for handling this uncertainty.

Chen et al. (2006) propose a fuzzy decision model based on linguistic values for determining supplier attributes, converting them into fuzzy numbers to facilitate ranking. It allows companies to rank suppliers more precisely than the conventional scoring technique, which oversimplifies decision factors.

Fuzzy-based models also incorporate weighting mechanisms to assign greater priorities to supplier attributes according to business objectives to enable a more strategic selection process.

A specific application of this model is in supply industries where the availability of suppliers is subject to forces beyond the control of any single organisation, e.g., fluctuations in raw material prices or geopolitical events. Fuzzy TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution) analysis, for instance, is used to allow decision-makers to rank the suppliers based on the closeness degree of proximity to what the company would consider a perfect supplier that presents the best compromise between cost, delivery time and quality variability. This result creates a more robust and flexible supplier network, thus reducing the risk of supply chain disruptions due to undependable suppliers.

2.1.2 Fuzzy Models for Supply Chain Aggregate Production Planning (SCAPP)

Other than supplier evaluation, fuzzy logic is also extensively used in the area of Supply Chain Aggregate Production Planning (SCAPP), where firms must decide on the ideal trade-off among production, inventory, and distribution under fuzzy demand circumstances. Conventional linear programming models presume a constant demand and certain resource availability, which results in inefficiency as a result of unforeseen alterations. Fuzzy logic overcomes this drawback by allowing decision-makers to work with uncertain, imprecise data, improving responsiveness to market fluctuations.

Sutthibutr et al. (2024) present a Multi-Objective Fuzzy Linear Programming model (MOFLP) that integrates cost minimization and risk management to develop a more efficient and resilient supply chain. Chance-Constrained Programming (CCP)² and Zimmermann's method³ are integrated into the model so that supply chain managers can

² Chance-Constrained Programming (CCP): An optimization method that ensures constraints are met with a specified probability under uncertainty.

³ Zimmermann's method: A fuzzy multi-objective optimization approach that balances conflicting goals by converting them into a single decision model.

determine optimal production schedules considering multiple conflicting goals, such as cost minimization with the ability to flexibly respond to unforeseen changes in demand.

Using triangular and trapezoidal fuzzy numbers, visible in Figure 3 and Figure 4, organisations formulate more responsive production strategies, which ensure that excessive costs remain at the minimum level while quality of service remains improved. Fuzzy programming finds real application in industries having unstable demand dynamics, such as retail, automotive, and electronic manufacturing. This will allow firms to get rid of both overproduction costs and stockouts through simulating uncertain demand trends and subsequently ensure better stock control with reduced holding costs and enhanced responsiveness to the consumers' demand.

Figure 3: Graph with triangular fuzzy number

Source: A Linear Programming Model with Fuzzy Arc for Route Optimization in the Urban Road Network, 2019

Figure 4: Graph with trapezoidal fuzzy number

Source: A Linear Programming Model with Fuzzy Arc for Route Optimization in the Urban Road Network, 2019

2.1.3 Fuzzy-Based resource allocation and logistics optimization

Another significant supply chain optimization application domain where fuzzy logic is utilised is resource planning and logistics management. Supply chain planners have to make decisions on transport routes, warehouse distribution, and human resource planning depending on dynamic constraints. Fuzzy logic is employed to represent those fuzzy variables, leading to cost-effective and efficient logistics management.

For instance, in transportation planning, organisations must plan optimum delivery routes for goods against unavoidable traffic, fuel costs, and truck supply. A fuzzy logic-based optimisation model can present linguistic variables (e.g., "low congestion", "medium congestion", "high congestion") and transform them into fuzzy numbers to

optimise dynamic routing. Logistics managers can dynamically reassign delivery schedules in real time and thus improve response times and decrease transportation costs.

Similarly, fuzzy models are applied to warehouse management to optimize space allocation as well as inventory replenishment. Warehouses apply fuzzy demand forecasting in order to allocate storage facilities to maximum utilisation, to reduce waste and also for increasing retrieval time. This is very crucial, when considering multi-echelon supply chains, as evident in Figure 5, where there are a number of distribution centres that require to optimize the movement of inventory on the basis of fuzzy demand rates.

Figure 5: Multi-echelon supply chains

Source: *Multi-echelon Inventory Models in "Materials Management"*, 2014

2.2 IoT-based supply chain management

IoT is the latest technology that is normally used in industry, and applications make present SCM better.

Internet of Things (IoT) was originally used in the 1990s. Most of the work was completed by the inventor IoT, "Kevin Ashton". He originated the term "The Internet of Things" to describe "a system where the Internet is connected to the physical world via ubiquitous sensors".

In the recent years, the authors of the article "IoT-based supply chain management: A systematic literature review" (2023) recognised that the general architecture of IoT has three layers:

1. Perception layer: The overall architecture of IoT is bottom-up in approach. The perception layer is the lowest layer. This layer is the physical layer of IoT's architecture. It is responsible for gathering data and physical parameters of the surrounding environment by using various sensors, actuators, and other intelligent devices.
2. Network Layer: The data received from the perception layer is forwarded and distributed to other network devices, servers, and applications for further processing through the network layer.
3. Application Layer: The application layer is the topmost layer of IoT architecture, and the purpose of this layer is to provide application-specific services to the end-users. This layer also contains programs and modules that firms or businesses use to view real-time data and make smart decisions for their business activities.

2.2.1 How IoT is transforming supply chains: top 10 applications for efficiency and security

On 6 November 2024, Georgia Collins, a journalist at “SupplyChain Digital”, published an article on the “Top 10: Uses of IoT in Supply Chains”.

Using her research as a basis, the 10 best ways to implement the IoT in supply chains are:

1. Real-time tracking and monitoring: With IoT sensors on vehicles and products, it is simple to determine the location in real time, thereby making it easy to track from the point of origin to the point of delivery. Giving enhanced visibility of inventory, loss protection, and effective delivery management. Companies such as DHL, Maersk, Amazon, and Nestlé are employing IoT for real-time monitoring and tracking of supply chains.
2. Predictive maintenance: Using IoT sensors once more, predictive maintenance can be carried out, identifying wear and tear on equipment so that the company can plan maintenance in advance. By doing this, companies such as Siemens and Caterpillar can minimize unplanned downtime, maintain smooth operations, and prolong equipment life.

Caterpillar is a case that has worked with Uptake to develop IoT-based predictive maintenance platforms. The joint platform aggregates real-time sensor data to enable predictive maintenance via the prediction of failure in advance.

3. **Warehouse management:** Through IoT devices used in warehouse management, business enterprises like Amazon, DHL, and Walmart are using RFID tags and sensors in an effort to improve warehouse functions. These technologies enable the tracking of stock levels, management of inventory, and automatic reorders in an effort to prevent stockouts as well as overstock conditions.
4. **Temperature and humidity control:** IoT technology is being used in food and pharma sectors to measure temperature, humidity, and other surrounding conditions. The firms are undertaking this in order to stay in quality regulation and avoid spoilage during transportation.
Hapag-Lloyd uses smart containers with IoT sensors positioned on them to track temperature and humidity. It has access to real-time information to keep its sensitive goods in ideal condition during transportation.
5. **Fleet management:** Businesses are utilising IoT in supply chain operations to manage their fleets in an effort to decrease routes, save fuel costs, and improve driver safety. By tracking driver behaviour, fuel consumption, and vehicle characteristics, IoT fleet management solutions improve these operations. DHL, Amazon, Walmart, UPS, Maersk, and FedEx are among the businesses that utilize IoT for fleet management.
6. **Demand forecasting:** In demand forecasting, IoT data, collected through sensors and networked devices, can forecast patterns of demand so that the companies can use their inventory more effectively and try to minimize their wastage.
Refined IoT solutions for demand forecasting are being applied by Amazon, Coca-Cola, Unilever, and Nestlé for data collection from diverse sources to assist companies in coordinating manufacturing schedules with consumer demand.
7. **Asset tracking and theft prevention:** Companies that ship valuable goods don't want to suffer theft or similar incidents during shipment; for this reason, these organisations are using IoT-based GPS trackers in their operations for anti-theft and asset tracking. Increased visibility minimizes the risk of loss and theft for businesses such as Bosch, DHL, Maersk, and Tech Mahindra, allowing them to act quickly if an asset strays (for whatever reason) from its intended route.
8. **Quality control and inspection:** Industrial businesses may increase product consistency and dependability while lowering recalls and defects by using IoT sensors for inspection and quality control in supply chain activities.
Businesses such as Maersk, Walmart, DHL, Siemens, and Bosch are revolutionising quality management processes throughout their supply chains.

9. Energy management: By monitoring energy consumption in warehouses, manufacturing facilities, and logistics fleets, IoT enables organisations to reduce carbon footprint, conserve energy costs, and gain enhanced sustainability.

Companies such as Schneider Electric, Siemens, and Amazon are decreasing their carbon footprint through energy consumption tracking, emissions, and supply chain waste.

10. Customer experience enhancement: Businesses like Amazon, DHL, FedEx, Coca-Cola, Levi's, L'Oréal, and Zara are enhancing the consumer experience by making it easier for them to give customers accurate delivery status updates and tracking.

L'Oréal, for instance, uses IoT technologies to track its inventory and keep an eye on real-time client feedback. Product sensors can be used to detect usage, and smart shelves provide real-time data so the business can offer a customised shopping experience.

2.2.2 IoT and the evolution of supply chain management: benefits, risks, and future prospects

With IoT, the operations of a supply chain would include automation that would decrease errors and improve productivity. Smart warehouses with Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) and robot picking systems will streamline warehouse operations with improved inventory management and reduced labour costs.

IoT-based predictive maintenance systems help the operators in preventing equipment failure within the factories and warehouses by monitoring sensor data in order to spot the early indicators of wear and tear. This type of preventive measure prevents unanticipated equipment failures, which otherwise would have brought the supply chain to a standstill.

Data collected by IoT devices in huge volumes enable the organisations to utilize big data analytics and AI to make better supply chain decisions. As observed, IoT data empower the firms to monitor the inventory, trace the performance of the supplier, and forecast potential bottlenecks far ahead of business interference.

Historical sales statistics are generally used in traditional supply chains to forecast future demand. This type of prevention often fails to meet expectations because it lacks predictability and this can cause inefficiencies. Using IoT, companies can look into real-time consumer behaviour, weather conditions, and market changes to make better demand

projections. These projections can reduce stockouts and overstocking, leading to better inventory management and lower holding costs.

Furthermore, smart contracts with blockchain technology integrated into the IoT domain can foster more trust and transparency in supply chain transactions. In this regard, real-time data entered on a decentralized ledger makes supply chain processes tamper-proof and auditable. This improves supplier accountability, reduces incidences of fraud, and assures adherence to government regulations.

Natural disasters, geopolitical events, or global pandemics can have devastating effects on business operations. IoT enhances supply chain resilience by enabling companies to identify risks early, respond swiftly, and implement contingency plans effectively. For instance, IoT-enabled warehouses and distribution centres could detect any discrepancy with the range of available stock, equipment malfunctions, and delays in logistics so that the firm can step in and help mitigate acts of disruption before more serious action is needed.

In global supply chains, IoT facilitates multi-tier supplier visibility, allowing businesses to keep track of sourcing actions along an ethical track. This is especially useful for those industries where sustainability and compliance standards are very rigid, which include fashion, electronics, and automotive manufacturing.

Despite the numerous advantages, implementing IoT in supply chain management is not without challenges. One of the primary concerns is high initial investment costs associated with IoT infrastructure, including sensor deployment, cloud integration, and cybersecurity measures. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) may find it difficult to allocate resources for full-scale IoT adoption.

Another challenge is data interoperability and integration. This problem stems from the fact that different supply chain actors use different IoT platforms and systems. This situation can lead to difficulties in understanding the exchanged data. With many supply chain players deploying different IoT platforms and systems, seamless data exchange is yet a Sisyphean task. Standardization of IoT protocols is necessary to achieve full interoperability and real-time information sharing across global supply networks.

IoT-based supply chains may also face serious cybersecurity threats. Since IoT devices continuously gather sensitive business data and trigger transmissions, they are said to be subject to cyber-attacks, hacking, and data breaches. Therefore, companies

should implement robust cybersecurity frameworks, protocols for encryption, and access controls to protect IoT networks from an array of potential threats.

Additionally, some companies may be hesitant to adopt IoT due to concerns over data privacy and proprietary information sharing. Based on the assumption that IoT-based SCM depends on collaborative data sharing, trust and transparency issues can inhibit all possible benefits from being realised via collaborative data sharing among suppliers, manufacturers, and logistic providers.

2.3 Big data analytics for decision-making in SCM

In today's modern digital world, we are witnessing an exponential spread of data-using. The recent expansion of the data-collecting dynamic has generated the birth of Big Data, a name given to refer to extremely large and complex sets of data that are too big to be processed or analysed using common data-processing programs.

The data sets are obtained from numerous sources consisting of structured data (e.g., databases), unstructured data (e.g., social media, emails, or videos), and semi-structured data (e.g., XML files).

Oracle Corporation, a global technology company specialising in database management, cloud computing, and enterprise software solutions, groups the defining attributes of Big Data in three “Vs”:

1. Volume, which means the immense amount of data that is being generated.
2. Variety, indicating the variety of sources of data.
3. Velocity, indicating the speed at which the data is being generated and processed.

To extract value from these datasets, organisations depend on Big Data Analytics, the systematic examination and interpretation of information to establish patterns, associations, and trends. Through the application of sophisticated methods such as machine learning, artificial intelligence (AI), predictive modelling, and real-time analytics, organisations can turn raw data into meaningful information that informs strategic decision-making (IBM, 2024). This analytical technique enables organisations to tap into information gathered from many sources like IoT sensors, social media usage, payments, and smart devices in an effort to become more efficient, customer-centric, and competitive (Google Cloud, 2024).

The impact of Big Data and its analytics extends across various industries. In supply chain management, companies use predictive analytics to forecast demand, optimize logistics routes, and minimise inventory costs.

In today's rapidly evolving business environment, supply chain management has become increasingly complex, and companies require more sophisticated tools and methods to maintain their operations cost-conscious⁴ and competitiveness. Big Data Analytics (BDA) transformed supply chain decision-making, as it enables companies to filter out huge volumes of data in real time and draw actionable intelligence which guides how their operations can become more efficient, resilient, and sustainable.

With the worldwide supply chains that generate vast quantities of structured and unstructured data from sensors, enterprise applications, customer purchases, and market trends, the ability to capture and analyse that data has become a matter of utmost importance to organisations that want to improve logistics, forecasting, and risk management.

Despite this, the most common use of Big Data Analytics for supply chain management is still direct to improve forecast accuracy. This can lead to a problem for some companies, in fact, the traditional forecasting models are deprived of the capability for the detection of volatility and complexity in today's markets and thus contribute to inefficiencies such as high inventory costs, overproduction, and stockouts.

Grasping the power of machine learning algorithms and advanced statistical calculation, Big Data Analytics enables organisations to analyse historical sales data, consumer behaviours, economic indicators, and even external factors like weather conditions or geopolitical events to generate more precise demand predictions.

This improved forecasting capability allows companies to develop numerous advantages. Using this, companies can better optimise their purchasing processes, reduce overstocking and eliminate waste, thereby achieving profitability and viability.

Beyond demand forecasting, Big Data Analytics will also be required to streamline logistics and inventory management. Supply chains have to be controlled dynamically, and decisions need to be made in real-time, and this can be achieved through the combination of IoT sensors, GPS, warehouse automation technology, and Big Data. What the IoT can do is strongly linked with Big Data Analysis, as I wrote in the paragraph "2.2.2 IoT and the evolution of supply chain management: benefits, risks, and future

⁴ Cost-conscious: having an awareness of costs, careful about spending.

prospects”: *“Data collected by IoT devices in huge volumes enable the organisations to utilize big data analytics and AI to make better supply chain decisions”*.

Collecting data without analysing it is useless and devoid of any logical sense.

Risk management is also one of the areas where Big Data Analytics has revolutionised supply chain decision-making. Supply chains are becoming more vulnerable to disruption due to natural disasters, political unrest, cyberattacks, and supplier failures. Traditional risk management approaches often rely on historical data and reactive measures, while BDA enables a proactive and predictive approach. By analysing huge amounts of data across multiple sources such as news articles, social media posts, and finance reports, companies are able to identify early warning signs of disruptions that could occur and develop contingency plans.

Breakthroughs in machine learning and artificial intelligence also facilitate Big Data Analytics in supply chain management by allowing automation and cognitive decision-making. AI-driven algorithms can scan immense amounts of data at speeds unknown before, picking up patterns and connections that elude human analysts. These capabilities extend beyond operations efficiency to strategic planning, allowing businesses to simulate different supply chain scenarios and evaluate the potential impact of various factors such as price fluctuations, changes in consumer demand, and supplier disruptions. With the inclusion of prescriptive analytics, businesses can receive real-time recommendations for the best action but also enhance responsiveness and agility in an increasingly uncertain business environment.

Despite its vast potential, the implementation of Big Data Analytics in supply chain management comes with several challenges.

One of the first obstacles has already been explained and cited by me in the paragraph “2.2.2 IoT and the evolution of supply chain management: benefits, risks, and future prospects”. The fact that different supply chain actors use different IoT platforms and systems can lead to difficulties in understanding the exchanged data. Non-standard protocol of data can create silos that hinder seamless data sharing and analysis.

Other than that, processing and dealing with large amounts of data require massive investment in cloud technology, analytics platforms, and skilled data scientists, which may be a capital and technical challenge for small businesses.

Data security and privacy also take over the agenda, with greater reliance on digital technology increasing supply chains vulnerability to the threat of hacking and stealing of data.

Ensuring compliance with data protection regulations while maintaining transparency and accessibility for authorized stakeholders is a delicate balance that organisations must navigate carefully.

The future of Big Data Analysis in supply chain management will be tremendously dependent on futuristic developments in technologies and on business needs.

Building autonomous supply chains driven by artificial intelligence and real-time data analytics has the potential to realize ultimate efficiency and decision-making with minimal intervention. Moreover, as sustainability increasingly becomes a priority on the business and consumer agenda, Big Data Analytics will be central to supporting green supply chain activity, reducing carbon footprint, and driving circular economy activity.

Quantum computing and other emerging technologies will also be able to further revolutionise the industry by making even more rapid and advanced data analysis possible, unlocking new possibilities for supply chain optimization.

Following the continuous evolution of technology, companies need to invest in the infrastructure, people, and strategy in order to realise the full creative potential of Big Data Analytics on supply chain decision-making.

2.4 Secure supply chain management with blockchain

More than ever, the concept of security invaded our lives. When someone starts a new chat using WhatsApp, he can read a message from Meta that reassures him they don't have the possibility to read the messages in the chat.

The security concept is not a main aspect only for Meta. This type of attention extends to all global companies running in the new world.

Obviously also the security of the supply chain has become a major concern for corporations worldwide.

Traditional SCM systems always present problems that result in inefficiencies, fraud, and lack of transparency that are ultimately converted into losses in terms of finance and reputation. Blockchain technology has arrived as a saviour that can turn these problems around by offering a decentralised, immutable, and highly secure platform for supply chain management.

2.4.1 What is the blockchain

Before I continue, I find it's important to try to better understand what the Blockchain is.

Blockchain is a digital system for recording transactions in a secure and transparent way. Instead of being stored in a single location, the information is copied and distributed between a network of computers.

New transactions are grouped into blocks. When that block fills up, it gets chained to the following one, creating the so-called Blockchain. Relying on cryptography and consensus mechanisms through decentralized computer networks, data integrity and immutability are guaranteed.

It's possible to see an example of a blockchain in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Example of a blockchain

Source: Zheng et al. 2016

Even though pre-Bitcoin blockchain concepts exist, starting with the Bitcoin whitepaper, published October 31st, 2008, blockchain technology started to be widely applied, and it now extends to supply chain management, healthcare records, and digital agreements, providing an unbreachable and decentralised way to store and authenticate data.

2.4.2 How the supply chain is being revolutionized by blockchain technology

Deloitte, a leading global consulting firm, is one of the first to highlight the potential of blockchain to facilitate security, transparency, and integrity of supply chain transactions. According to Deloitte, blockchain offers a "single version of the truth" with fewer intermediaries and human-dependent verification procedures and greater stakeholder trust. This is particularly significant in the industries where adherence to the regulations, anti-fraud protection, and traceability are of the essence.

Using the distributed ledger mechanism of blockchain, companies can securely log commodity transaction movement, verify legitimacy, and protect themselves from imitations.

Another important advantage of blockchain over SCM is that it can enrich data integrity and safety. Traditional supply chains rely on numerous centralised databases that are susceptible to cyber-attacks, data breaches, and manipulation. Blockchain makes all transactions cryptographically encrypted, time-stamped, and immutable. Consequently, Blockchain makes unauthorised modifications almost impossible and reduces the risk of fraud significantly.

Another important role is played by smart contracts, contracts inserted into the blockchain code. I have already introduced this type of contract in the paragraph “2.2.2 IoT and the evolution of supply chain management: benefits, risks, and future prospects”. Smart contracts allow payment, compliance verification, and inventory control in an automated way.

These contracts do not reduce only operating costs, says Deloitte, they also eliminate inefficiencies due to paperwork and human error. These contracts eliminate the need for intermediaries, reducing delays and operational costs while ensuring compliance with contractual agreements.

For instance, at the instant a consignment reaches its destination, a smart contract can instantly make the payment with minimal third-party authentication.

By allowing an easier interaction between manufacturers, suppliers, and logistics providers, blockchain makes the supply chain system more transparent and accountable.

Last but not least, Blockchain use in sustainable supply chain management is becoming increasingly widespread and functional. By providing a transparent and open record of environmental impact, blockchain enables companies to track carbon emissions, ensure ethical sourcing, and reduce waste, aligning with global sustainability goals.

Though it has some benefits, blockchain in supply chains has some challenges. Scalability is a primary one. Older blockchains like Bitcoin and Ethereum only accommodate limited numbers of transactions per second. This causes bottlenecks, especially for high-volume businesses.

Interoperability with other blockchain platforms and current supply chain software is an issue as well. This concept is not new; I have mentioned this problem several times in the last paragraphs. Many companies use different technologies, making

it difficult to achieve seamless integration. A possible, but not simple, answer to this issue is creating universal blockchain standards and protocols.

Apart from this, another problem is that implementation costs can be very prohibitive. However, of all the challenges, this is the one that should scare companies the least. In fact, Deloitte notes that organisations that invest in blockchain-based supply chain solutions can gain an important advantage through increased security, compliance and efficiency. This advantage may easily transform into higher earnings and lower expenses.

Instead, one challenge that should scare companies is the legal and regulatory ambiguities hindering blockchain adoption. Various jurisdictions have varying laws on data privacy, enforceability of smart contracts, and record-keeping using blockchain. Businesses have to navigate such legal frameworks in an attempt to achieve compliance and realise blockchain potential.

The potential of blockchain in supply chains is vast. Blockchain scalability is studied to be improved by Layer-2 solutions, technologies designed to improve the scalability and efficiency of blockchain networks by processing transactions off the main blockchain (Layer-1) while still benefiting from its security and interoperability via cross-chain protocols so that data can be easily transferred on different supply chain platforms.

While there are challenges still ahead, the potential of blockchain for greater transparency, security, and efficiency makes it a worthwhile investment for future supply chain management. If the companies continue to explore the potential of blockchain, collaboration among supply chain participants, technologists, and regulators will be required to drive mass adoption.

3. Artificial Intelligence in supply chain management

3.1 A long-standing relationship

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into supply chain management (SCM) is not a recent trend of the 21st century but rather a progression that has its origins in the 1990s. During this period, researchers and industry professionals began exploring AI-driven techniques to optimize various aspects of the supply chain, particularly in decision-making, forecasting, and automation.

Early applications of AI that were used in SCM included predominantly neural networks and intelligent decision-support systems, as highlighted in some fundamental studies from the 1990s.

Horris C. Bung's publication in 1995 refers to an early application of neural networks in supply chain operations. Human brain-like processes replicated by neural networks have been largely responsible for managing the complexity associated with logistics, demand planning, inventory management, and transportation planning.

The potential for developing artificial systems capable of processing advanced, nonlinear supply chain relationships was recognised for the first time.

The study highlights some of the most significant benefits of employing neural networks in supply chain management and demonstrates their potential for creating efficiency, flexibility, and decision-making capability overall. The most effective application include pattern recognition, demand forecasting, inventory optimization, dynamic adaptability, and supplier and logistics optimization.

One of the most significant contributions of neural networks to supply chain management is their ability to detect complex patterns and improve forecasting demand.

Traditional models of forecasting depend on historical sales data and linear assumptions and do not hold up when market dynamics change. Neural networks, on the other hand, examine vast amounts of real-time and historical data to identify intricate trends and connections that may elude more conventional models. By learning from past fluctuations and external factors, such as economic indicators or seasonal shifts in demand, these types of machine learning models provide businesses with more reliable demand forecasts that avoid overstocking or deficits.

Inventory management is another crucial area where neural networks offer substantial benefits. By analysing historical stock levels, sales cycles, and demand

variation patterns, these models help companies decide on the most favourable inventory levels.

A proper supply-demand balance is extremely important in terms of maintaining minimum costs with avoidance of stockouts, keeping products ready when needed without unnecessary storage costs. Because neural networks refine their predictions by continually learning more, they maximise the efficiency of inventories, allowing businesses to operate with leaner supply chains.

A major advantage of neural networks over traditional rule-based systems is that neural networks are dynamically flexible. Supply chains operate within highly volatile regimes where random shocks, represented by delays, shortages, or geopolitical events, can seriously affect operations. Compared to static models requiring manual realignment, neural networks learn and respond to new information in real time. In this way, businesses are able to respond ahead of time to emerging challenges, overall resilience, and reduce operational risk.

Beyond internal supply chain operations, neural networks also play a crucial role in supplier and logistics optimization. Companies have to manage large volumes of suppliers, monitor performance and deliver products on time. Artificial intelligence models assist in quantifying the reliability of suppliers by monitoring past history of performance, forecasting potential delays, and offering back-up suppliers if required. Further, in logistics, neural networks also improve delivery routes, considering traffic patterns, weather conditions, and transportation costs.

Another major contribution from the late 1990s was the development of Intelligent Decision Support Systems (IDSS) for e-supply chains. As emphasised in a report prepared by five experts in 1999 titled "Intelligent Decision Support for the e-Supply Chain", the advent of e-commerce and digital transformation introduced new challenges to supply chain management, necessitating the adoption of Intelligent Decision Support Systems (IDSS).

These IDSS-based systems supported decision-making by integrating data, real-time monitoring, collaboration, and risk mitigation.

Consolidation of information from various sources, including market trends, supplier databases, and logistics networks, was one of the greatest strengths of IDSS.

Business organizations, by this data-driven approach, automated procurement, production, and distribution for overall efficiency.

Risk assessment capabilities driven by artificial intelligence also facilitated companies to simulate probable disruptions, compare alternatives, and act ahead of time to develop supply chain resilience. IDSS brought the supply chain management to a turning point, providing the companies with the flexibility and intelligence needed to navigate a more complex and fast-moving global market. IDSS led the way to today's AI-driven supply chains that constantly expand and evolve.

Despite being applied in different contexts (traditional supply chains and e-SCM), neural networks and Intelligent Decision Support Systems (IDSS) share a common goal: maximizing efficiency through AI-driven decision-making. These developments highlight the fact that AI is not just a supplementary tool but a fundamental enabler of automation, predictive accuracy, and responsiveness in supply chain management.

Neural networks boost predictive demand, inventory management, and supplier coordination, while IDSS aggregates real-time information for strategic planning and risk minimization. These AI-based methodologies complement each other to increase responsiveness, with supply chains capable of anticipating disruptions and market fluctuations.

These early endeavours during the 1990s were the building blocks of modern AI-driven supply chains. While modern AI technologies have the possibility to have at their disposal several robust technologies such as big data, cloud computing, and advanced machine learning algorithms, the fundamental concepts of AI-driven supply chain optimization remain rooted in the innovations of the past.

By acknowledging this long-standing relationship, we are better able to understand how AI has consistently evolved to become better and to enhance efficiency, resilience, and responsiveness in supply chains.

3.2 The enormous impact of the last few years

Trying to capture what AI represents in 2025 is an immense undertaking, which risks being redundant. The mark AI is leaving on the world when you read these words is already different from the one it left when I wrote this sentence, constantly shifting and reshaping itself in ways beyond our grasp.

The Artificial Intelligence is a "code-and-algorithms living being" with endless potential. It is growing at a pace that overpushes not only our expertise but also our imagination. It

transcends former limits, redefines the edge of possibility, and brings a transformation trail behind.

3.2.1 Rethinking supply chains with Artificial Intelligence

For the above reasons and the underlying complexity of the topic, I will limit myself to exposing how and why the combination of AI and SCM has been a turning point in the way companies conceptualise, implement, and optimize their logistics networks. The objective is to understand how, in an environment of global uncertainty and technological revolution, the application of Artificial Intelligence in supply chains has not only improved operations; it has revolutionised them.

New technologies such as Large Language Models (LLMs), ChatGPT and generative AI have extended AI capabilities beyond traditional automation and predictive tasks into higher-order decision-making, planning coordination, and knowledge development.

As highlighted by Wang et al. (2023), the new generative AI technologies are being extensively researched for the way they can improve transparency, the quality of decisions, and strategic coordination across supply chains.

Their research report identifies some of the key strengths of generative AI in SCM, such as demand forecasting via automation, risk detection through natural language processing (NLP), and human-AI collaboration to solve problems and make strategic decisions.

In my point of view, the NLP risk detection is one of the most interesting uses of generative AI in SCM. Wang et al. (2023) states that generative AI solutions such as ChatGPT are able to browse through vast sets of unstructured text-based information, e.g., news reports, supplier correspondence, social media posts, etc., to identify early warning signals of potential disruptions. These risk situations involve risks of geopolitical tensions, raw material supply problems, or supplier default. Using risk detection through natural language processing, companies are providing increased supply chain visibility and responding quicker, from intelligence-driven data, that generate an increased overall level of flexibility and resiliency.

Additionally, generative AI systems can facilitate the communication between supply chain ecosystems by translating intricate technical information delivered in an understandable language and producing real-time reports and recommendations (Wang et

al., 2023). This would be particularly critical in globalized supply chains where coordination among advanced players is very high.

At the operational level, AI is also revolutionising the way companies can optimize route optimization, quality inspection, and fraud detection through structured and unstructured data using machine learning and the aforementioned NLP algorithms.

Meanwhile, Sharma et al. (2023) also point out how increasing applications of AI in supply chains are being propelled by demands for greater agility, cost reductions, and sustainability.

In their systematic literature review, they explain how AI facilitates five key supply chain functions:

1. Demand forecasting,
2. Inventory management,
3. Choosing suppliers,
4. Optimizing logistics,
5. Customer service.

Their research throws light on how AI technology in the form of deep learning, reinforcement learning, and computer vision enables eradicating human bias, optimizing real-time choices, and achieving high efficiencies in planning and forecasting. The review also evokes the synergy of action among AI and Industry 4.0 technologies like IoT, blockchain, and cyber-physical systems that collectively make highly flexible and integrated supply chains.

Although promising, however, several studies and research papers, like Wang and Sharma, have admitted that there are still barriers to entry. These barriers, which range from low data quality and low AI literacy among supply chain actors to ethical issues related to transparency, explainability, and algorithm bias, inhibit the mass adoption of AI technology.

These remaining obstacles show the necessity for fair AI governance, interdisciplinarity, and investments in digital capability to ensure AI makes supply chain performance simpler, not more complex.

To overcome these issues, it's important to use AI responsibly, bring together cross-disciplinary collaboration, and invest in more advanced digital capabilities and tools. Only then can AI truly improve supply chain performance, rather than create new problems.

3.2.2 AI under pressure during the COVID-19 crisis

The supply chain resilience capability of the AI technologies emerged especially strongly with the COVID-19 pandemic.

The global health crisis, as Awan et al. (2022) explain, exposed deep weaknesses in traditional supply chains, such as their over-reliance on lean inventory models, thin visibility across levels, and failure to react rapidly to demand and supply shocks. Despite all these constraints, AI emerged as a key enabler of resilience by enabling companies to predict disruptions in advance, simulate risk scenarios, and re-synthesize dynamic supply networks.

Research studies done by Awan et al. (2022) examine real usage during the pandemic, where AI has been utilised to monitor inventory shortfalls, reroute logistics, and recognise volatility in demand better. For example, machine learning software helped companies in assessing alternative sources of supply and streamlining procurement procedures in response to lockdown-related factory closures.

Predictive analytics also helped make efficient use of limited resources such as medical supplies and raw materials by estimating the size of the consumption geographically and span-wise as well.

Another important AI contribution during COVID-19 was probably to provide end-to-end supply chain visibility. Powered by IoT sensor data, cloud infrastructure, and AI dashboards, companies were able to achieve real-time situational awareness and enhance supplier, manufacturer, and distributor coordination. These abilities not only responded to near-term disruption but also guided long-term strategic transformation towards resilient and digital supply chains.

Of particular importance is how the crisis has made companies more aware that resilience is not a choice but a strategic top-line imperative.

The COVID-19 pandemic was a stress test and confirmed the strategic value of AI in supply chain management. Businesses that had already adopted AI technology prior to the pandemic performed better, recovered quicker, and even experienced competitive gains.

The integration of intelligent forecasting, adaptive planning, and autonomous decision-making technologies has been proven not only as a strategic step towards crisis management but also as an advanced approach that is transforming supply chain design for the future. As a result, the market has quickly realised that AI-driven resilience is no

longer a crisis response but a necessary and proactive capability in the contemporary supply chain.

3.3 Sailing into the future: how AI is reshaping global shipment and logistics

The global shipping and logistics sector, once the stronghold of traditional practices, manual follow-ups, and linear operations, is being revolutionised to its very core by the introduction of Artificial Intelligence (AI). This technology is not just digitalising but is a qualitative leap in operational intelligence, predictive capacity, and strategic coordination.

AI use in global logistics is increasingly being seen as an underlying driver to minimize shipment routing, minimize environmental impact, enhance real-time tracking, and streamline port efficiency.

Shipment monitoring and route planning is one of the biggest areas where AI is revolutionising logistics.

Shukla et al. (2023) recognise that AI products are taking levels of efficiency to unprecedented levels in freight logistics through the use of sophisticated algorithms that consume enormous datasets from GPS, weather systems, fuel consumption rates, and real-time traffic flows.

These intelligent systems provide dynamic route optimization in real time, predicting delays, examining traffic congestion, and suggesting alternative routes. This flexibility not only reduces delivery time but also fuel consumption and cost optimization.

Deep learning and reinforcement learning algorithms are increasingly being utilised to detect patterns in transit behaviour and historical disruptions so that predictive logistics can be attained with reduced uncertainty in shipment delivery.

Furthermore, the use of AI in logistics enables the shift from reactive to proactive management. AI-based real-time tracking systems enable logistics companies to gain multi-faceted visibility of all the nodes in the supply chain. This visibility allows for the accurate prediction of Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) and of vehicle service, and shipment deviation alerting well in advance. For example, machine learning will predict whether a container will be delayed due to customs clearance issues based on historical experience and policy changes, allowing shippers to reroute or amend documents in advance (Shukla et al., 2023).

Implementing AI-powered dashboards integrates such information and offers actionable insights, allowing supply chain decision-makers to make better-informed decisions and reduce the risk of human error.

Such technological potential is particularly pronounced in maritime shipping, long notorious for elevated operational complexity and low visibility.

AI technology in maritime logistics, Kaid et al. (2023) contend, is revolutionizing port operations through the use of smart sensors, autonomous navigation, and port call optimization software. For instance, AI-driven traffic management systems are being implemented to monitor port congestion levels and recommend ship speed changes to align with berth schedules. This reduces idling time and fuel consumption while facilitating a smoother flow of goods. Kaid et al. (2023) also explain that predictive analytics enables port authorities to manage the flow of containers, predicting load/unload times, and automatic scheduling in the storage yard. These technologies are necessary in order to optimize turnaround times and prevent operational bottlenecks.

Another priority area and increasing key is how AI is assisting in enabling green shipping operations by making "just-in-time" (JIT) arrivals possible. The adoption of this management philosophy allows ships to avoid the dramatic situation where they are sailed at a higher-than-normal speed to reach the port, wrongly thinking it is free, only to discover it completely full and with the knowledge that they have wasted fuel unnecessarily and polluted more for nothing.

With JIT arrivals, ships can travel slower and produce fewer emissions, because they have the guarantee that once they arrive at the port, it will not be congested.

Combined with weather-optimal routing and AI-powered fuel consumption modelling, maritime logistics stands at the threshold of an era of green transformation. Oceanographic and meteorological data, for example, are used by algorithms to calculate optimal energy-conserving routes for container ships. These capabilities come most into focus for global climate objectives and frameworks like the IMO 2030 and 2050 targets.

Muntean et al. (2022) describe how AI models are being developed to model shipping emissions and determine mitigation measures towards carbon accounting and sustainability monitoring. AI-powered emissions monitoring software has the potential to allow carriers and terminal operators to monitor carbon emissions in real-time, optimize routes or engine utilisation, and adhere to changing environmental regulations.

At the same time, the development of AI-powered and IoT-enabled smart ports is transforming the shipping terminal logistics environment. Muntean et al. (2022) note that

AI algorithms are crucial for traffic flow management, autonomous cranes, and intelligent warehouse systems in green port development. The systems rely on real-time information to reduce crane travel time, energy usage, and yard congestion via optimized container stacking and recovery. AI also enables collaboration among port stakeholders, including shipping lines, customs, and terminal operators, via interoperable digital platforms allowing end-to-end coordination. Cross-functional visibility reduces delays while enhancing security and compliance for international shipments. While these academic sources provide a wide-angle lens on AI's transformative potential, complementary insights from industry stakeholders help to highlight the practical implications of this shift.

For example, the MSC blog (2024) explains how AI is used in real shipping operations to enhance fleet management, document automation, and decision-making on board the ships. The organisation talks about using AI in forecasting the needs of ships' maintenance, reducing downtime, and enhancing maritime safety by detecting faults in mechanical systems early.

Despite all the obvious advantages, nonetheless, logistics deployment of AI is not problem-free. As has already been mentioned so many times before, efficient utilisation of AI technologies requires massive investments in digital infrastructure, quality data, and competent staff able to interpret AI-generated insights. In addition, data privacy, cyber threats, and ethical AI management remain matters of concern.

As mentioned also in previous paragraphs, there is an urgent need for regulatory requirements and industry standards that offer interoperability, transparency, and equitable access to AI tools. Solving these issues is critical to realising the full potential of AI without causing harm and unintended effects.

The differential rate of adoption of AI among regions and companies is another central factor. While large shipping operators and large ports are quickly adopting AI systems, small shipping operators and port facilities in emerging markets face barriers related to cost, technical capacity, and institutional readiness issues. This digital divide may potentially exacerbate trade competitiveness disparities in the world unless balanced with inclusive innovation policy interventions and capacity-building programmes.

Despite these obstacles, many important researchers collectively suggest that AI is not only an automatization, but a changer of maritime logistics. The evidence from the MSC blog also shows that the changes mentioned above are no illusions but reality, which already have an effect on the practice of top world shippers. As logistics networks become

ever more complex and interconnected, AI will serve as the cognitive core that sustains operational resilience.

The challenge of the future will be to find solutions to the problems which now exist so that the potential of the AI can be realised.

3.3.1 Case Study: AI's role in Maersk's shipping and supply chain

In the past two years, artificial intelligence (AI) applications have revolutionised supply chain management (SCM) and many other maritime logistics practices.

Par excellence exemplars thereof include Maersk revolution, which ranks among the global shipping firms that have employed AI to maximize its efficiency, flexibility, and satisfaction of the customer in their international operations. This innovation, which was as much a product of innovation as it was a response to need, is part of a wider trend in the logistics world in which traditional ways of doing things are being supplanted by forward-looking systems with foresight and real-time decision-making (Rahou & Chikhi, 2023).

Maersk's approach is based on optimizing seaborne routes, an age-old logistical challenge brought about by volatile fuel prices, congested ports, and unpredictable weather. With artificial intelligence-driven route optimization software, Maersk can repeatedly examine factors such as port capacity, ship capacity, weather conditions, and fuel prices to determine the optimal shipping routes. These decisions are recalculated dynamically with real-time data feeds so that crew on ships can reroute sailing routes mid-journey in the event of a delay or environmental risk. This adaptive-to-adaptive routing reorientation not only reflects Maersk's vision for long-term sustainability but is also fuel-efficient, as explained by Rahou and Chikhi (2023).

The second critical application area of AI is container and shipment tracking. With IoT sensor and AI-fortified tracking software technology, Maersk has offered greater end-to-end visibility in its containers along global supply chains. These technologies are made available to customers as well as internal stakeholders to track containers in real-time and receive predictive estimates of arrival and probable delays. Furthermore, historical data analysis supports proactive risk mitigation by identifying patterns in shipment delays, enabling Maersk to reroute a container or reschedule before a disruption. Such transparency is required in a customer-centric culture where requests are more and more about predictability and precision.

Demand forecasting is another domain where Maersk utilises the analytical capability of AI. Historical shipment volumes and outside market indicators are used by AI models to predict transport demand with a level of granularity previously unattainable (Rahou & Chikhi, 2023). This allows Maersk to optimize its fleet deployment and allocate resources more efficiently, ensuring that capacity meets actual demand without unnecessary overhead. Forecast models improve with machine learning as additional data is accumulated, resulting in enhanced accuracy. This forms a cycle where planning strategy and cost savings are directly driven by AI.

In Maersk warehouse logistics, artificial intelligence (AI) software is employed to automate picking, efficiently manage the inventory, and routing-deliverance optimization. AI systems reduce processing time and order reliability by leveraging maximum storage forecasting and inventory turnover forecasting. Computer program-based AI warehouse automation optimizes functions but also maximizes a green logistics system with reduced waste and minimized energy usage. These developments are pivotal in enabling JIT delivery arrangements that are consistent with lean supply chain approaches.

In the field of customer experience, Maersk utilises chatbots and virtual assistants powered by AI to provide 24/7 support. The systems answer a wide range of questions, from tracking to documentation, and are capable of learning from interactions to improve response accuracy over time and can get better over time to be more precise in responses. Beyond convenience, the systems enhance experience via context-based responding in real-time, hence reducing response time and allowing human agents to handle complicated cases.

A truly revolutionary use, for instance, is Maersk's use of digital twins, which simulate entire port operations and shipping logistics in a virtual environment. They allow the company to simulate various scenarios, e.g., strikes, bad weather, or traffic congestion, and hence enable it to choose its best course of action prior to actual-life consequences. As Hofman (2024) points out, through the adoption of digital twins, port operators can shift from using spreadsheets for manual planning to dynamic real-time feedback simulation. As Krishnan Srinivasan, Chief Data Officer at Maersk, notes, this capability transforms planning processes that once took days into operations that now take hours.

Besides that, AI provides end-to-end visibility and anticipatory solutions to problems across the supply chain. With AI-powered predictive analytics and sensor data integration, Maersk can detect precursor warning signs for disruptions such as customs delays or container backlogs and act before they escalate. This strengthens the global

shipping logistics and allows Maersk to offer the reliability of the service even in the most vulnerable of moments.

It's important to note that Maersk continues to distinguish the value of human brainpower during these important technology transitions. Instead of wholeheartedly adopting automation, the firm promotes a hybrid model where human judgement augments AI. "We are making sure that humans are complementary to the technology," Srinivasan explains.

The company's approach illustrates that the future of shipping is neither purely digital nor purely human, but a strategic convergence of both.

This hybrid MAERSK approach is not the only one; it is certainly the one that Maersk recognises and communicates, but many researchers describe how Maersk employed another type of hybrid architecture composed by "Cloud-Based Blockchain Integrated with Machine Learning (CBML)".

In the study "*A Case Study of How Maersk Adopts Cloud-Based Blockchain Integrated with Machine Learning for Sustainable Practices*" Wong et al. (2023) examine how Maersk has strategically adopted this architecture to improve supply chain sustainability, transparency, and efficiency.

This model leverages the decentralised and tamper-proof nature of blockchain to secure and track logistics data across the shipping ecosystem, while machine learning algorithms extract patterns and predictive insights from real-time and historical data. These together support real-time decision-making, document efficiency, and fraud control in global supply chain management.

While deployment of CBML is with no influential technical or organizational hindrance, one of the significant limitations is data quality. Supply chains may have divergent and interconnected streams of data that compromise data recording as well as AI model integrity. Inconsistent or poorly structured data having incorrect content can produce erroneous forecasts as well as decrease system reliability.

Both scalability and latency are of concern too. As artificial intelligence models and data-hungry blockchain networks grow in size, the infrastructure must be able to support increasing levels of processing, bandwidth, and storage requirements. The scalability problem is dealt with by Maersk by leveraging the ability of Microsoft Azure cloud infrastructure, which allows providing off-chain storage along with elastic scaling of processing load.

Moreover, while blockchain does give immutability, it makes error correction harder. To ensure that smart contracts never fail, Maersk uses formal verification before deployment. Energy consumption, especially where both AI and blockchain are being utilized at the same time, is an environmental concern, being reduced somewhat by cloud optimization.

The other challenges that prevail are prohibitively expensive deployment and shortages of AI skills. Maersk experience informs re-skilling and norm regulation as the solution for balancing technology with man-oriented operations.

In conclusion, Maersk's innovation proves how artificial intelligence, if appropriately paired with technologies like machine learning and blockchain, can reimagine logistics across the globe. By integrating a hybrid approach that harmonizes human expertise with technological precision, Maersk ensures an innovation that benefits operational performance, and at the same time, it benefits also strategic foresight.

Maersk's model is not limited to create resilience and sustainability, but it also sets the benchmark for intelligent, human-driven supply chains in the future.

3.4 Artificial intelligence in the food supply chain from automation to ethics

Food supply chain (FSC) is a complex net-like structure covering the whole food chain from farm to plate. Efficiency, sustainability, and resilience of FSC are of prime importance, not just for business success but also for public health and global food security. The FSCs of today, however, are confronted with unprecedented global challenges in the shape of climate change, geopolitics, pandemics, and changing consumer aspirations. These pressures expose the vulnerabilities of the supply chain, particularly because the nature of the food is such that it becomes perishable, and there arise higher demands on safety, traceability, and sustainability (Halder et al., 2025).

AI has emerged as a revolutionary force capable of addressing these challenges across all stages of the FSC. In agriculture, artificial intelligence technologies include predictive analytics, robots, and machine learning that facilitate precision farming technology in motion. Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT)-based technologies enable real-time monitoring of the soil, pest infestation, and water irrigation efficiency. Technologies, apart from optimizing yield, minimise environmental impact by optimal use of resources (Halder et al., 2025; Kollia et al., 2021).

Along the supply chain route of the food, AI also optimizes safety and efficiency. In logistics, smart cold chain management employs IoT-sensors and predictive algorithms to monitor temperature and humidity in a bid to preserve food quality during transit and storage. AI also enables route optimization based on real-time traffic, weather, and fuel, reducing emissions and delivery time. In retailing, AI-powered demand forecasting models designed using LSTM⁵ and CNNs⁶ reduce overstocking and wastage by matching stock against forecasted customer behaviours. Deep learning-based optical inspection systems also ensure safety and freshness for the product.

The significance of AI extends into food traceability. Supply chains are evolving towards "Traceability 3.0", a phase characterised by AI-powered systems capable of dynamic decision-making and real-time anomaly detection. These systems are imperative to achieve maximum transparency, improve recall efficiency optimization, and ensure compliance with food safety regulations (Manning et al., 2022). A strong system for meeting these needs is the blockchain implementation, which makes traceability data evident and verifiable, helping to win the trust of consumers.

AI is also crucial in risk management. Systemic shocks such as the war in Ukraine or the COVID-19 pandemic can severely challenge the classical models.

Underscores the need for proactive rather than reactive responses in this scenario. The "ripple effect", wherein an intervention in a node has repercussions across the entire supply chain, requires predictive systems able to identify early warning signals. Trollman (2024) proposes integrating Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA) with AI models in order to infer causal properties of supply chain failure based on expert knowledge to determine predictability and credibility.

Feature extraction is one of the most influential contributory elements towards the achievement of performance of AI in FSCs. Contrary to conventional automated work likely to exclude contextual factors, feature selection utilising QCA is focused on interpretability and applicability in actual application. This method allows the AI models to respond more ethically and truthfully, especially in higher-risk areas involving the well-being and health of the public. Application of human judgement gives assurance that AI

⁵ Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks are a kind of recurrent neural network (RNN) that can remember information over a long period, which makes them great for predicting future values in time-series data.

⁶ Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are deep learning models particularly effective at recognising spatial patterns in data, such as identifying features in images or structured datasets.

systems are well trained by authentic and valid data, mitigating the risks of overfitting or biased outputs.

To support transparency and trustworthiness, Explainable AI (XAI⁷) approaches are being pushed increasingly across the food sector. By revealing feature paths and understandable models, stakeholders like regulators, supply chain operators, and farmers can see how forecasts are generated. Manning et al. (2022) consider that such explainability is not a technical courtesy but an ethical requirement, especially for choices that may influence food safety or fairness of distribution. The ethical concerns are the substance of ethical AI use in food.

Manning et al. (2022) provide a standard ethical framework on the basis of key principles:

- Explainability,
- Accountability,
- Accessibility,
- Responsibility.

These values help align technological innovations with broader societal goals, ensuring that AI use does not put disfavoured parties at a disadvantage or cause harm to consumer welfare. The potential use of opaque “black box” algorithms raises concerns, especially when such systems influence decisions about recalls, safety alerts, or sourcing. For these reasons, ethical AI must be explainable, auditable, and regulatory compliant.

Security and privacy are also the major areas of concern in technologically progressive FSCs too. As already explained in some previous paragraphs, the widespread use of IoT and cloud platforms introduces risks of cyberattacks and data hacking.

Halder et al. (2025) propose AI-driven security measures with real-time anomaly detection, encryption-based channel communication, and blockchain-secured authentications. Apart from the protection of confidential business data, these measures also offer system integrity and reliability from farm to fork.

Some of the “fresh” developments include building Secure Social Industrial Internet of Things (SIIoT) platforms. These platforms integrate blockchain, artificial intelligence, and Internet of Things technologies to provide end-to-end visibility and control throughout the whole FSC. Pre-empting downtime becomes a reality in cold supply

⁷ Explainable AI (XAI) refers to a class of artificial intelligence systems designed to make their decision-making processes transparent and interpretable to humans, enhancing trust, accountability, and ethical alignment in critical domains such as healthcare, finance, and food supply chains.

chains through real-time monitoring of environmental conditions using analytics in combination with forecasts, while all transactions are made tamper-resistant through blockchain logging. All these new technologies make it possible to support sustainability, security, and public health programmes by maintaining the quality of perishable products throughout their whole life cycle (Halder et al., 2025).

However, the use of AI in FSCs is not without its challenges. The very high cost of deployment, especially to Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), dissuades them from their bulk usage. In most poor or rural societies, infrastructure for technology is underdeveloped, creating a digital divide. Further, it has a huge capability deficit so that most actors in the food business cannot install and utilize AI systems proficiently.

To counter these, it requires a multi-perspective solution involving numerous players. Interdisciplinary cooperation among farmers, distributors, policymakers, technologists, and consumers can help ensure that AI systems are co-designed as responsive, inclusive, and ethical. Participatory design approaches of this type not only encourage contextualisation of systems but also enable greater user trust and ownership. As Manning et al. (2022) note, integrated technical development with social and ethical principles is the recipe for sustainable use of AI.

Above all, the future of AI in FSCs lies in hybrid systems that take advantage of both machine efficiency and human intelligence. Rather than emphasising total automation, better systems use AI as an aid to human judgement, upholding it and not eroding it. For example, whereas a computer system might detect a probable spoilage event in transit, it would be human contextual decision-making that would ultimately decide whether to reroute a shipment considering logistical, economic, and social factors.

Trollman (2024) and Manning et al. (2022) both recommend such human-AI partnerships as the best and most ethical approach to handling resilient food supply chains.

In conclusion, the application of AI in food supply chains is a revolution towards smart, adaptive, and ethical systems. From optimizing agricultural productivity and logistics efficiency to transparency, security, and risk management, AI is both an enabling technology and a strategic enabler. However, its full potential will be only realised by embracing the culture of inclusive design, responsible regulation, and participative involvement among all stakeholders. As the global food system is building up cumulative stresses, AI brings innovation but also a route to resilience, justice, and trust.

3.4.1 Case Study: IBM Food Trust & Walmart's AI-driven supply chain

In recent years, blockchain and Artificial Intelligence (AI) integration has been at the forefront of revolutionising food supply chains, with Walmart and IBM standing at the forefront of this transformation. Their collaborative effort, IBM Food Trust, is a benchmark towards a smarter, more transparent, and more secure food system. This partnership not only enhances traceability and food safety but also redefines the potential of digital technologies to streamline logistics, foster consumer trust, and promote sustainable behaviours.

Walmart, known globally for its logistical prowess, started experimenting with blockchain as early as 2016, jointly testing with IBM and Tsinghua University on two major pilot projects: a pilot project on mangoes to be imported from Latin America and the other on pork products to be imported from China. These pilots were intended to solve the long-standing issue of traceability along the food supply chain, especially in the aftermath of a succession of food safety scandals across the world (Tan et al., 2018).

Prior to blockchain, tracing the origin of a mango in Walmart's supply chain required nearly seven days. With blockchain, this time was reduced to just 2.2 seconds, demonstrating the potential of the technology to enhance speed, accuracy, and efficiency (IBM, 2023). This time reduction is more exponentially than we can imagine. In the food supply chain sector, this kind of innovation is on a par with the invention of the internal combustion engine or oil refining and other similar ones. The implementation of blockchain reduced the traceability time by approximately 99.9996%, a near-total elimination of delay in tracking product origin.

AI, blockchain, and cloud computing are utilised by the IBM Food Trust platform to create an immutable ledger of food supply chain transactions. That is, every shift along the journey of a product, from farm to fork, is being tracked and traceable in real time. Each of the players in the supply chain, farmer, processor, distributor, or retailer, contributes to an open, shared system with data. This drastically reduces the risk of information asymmetry and increases visibility (Tan et al., 2018).

One of the major apparent benefits that IBM Food Trust has is that it is able to make predictions with the help of AI. By analysing historical data, climatic trends, and logistic trends, Walmart will be in a position to take proactive action through risk mitigation through the platform. For instance, AI can detect anomalies such as delayed delivery,

potential spoilage through temperature fluctuations, or odd behaviour from the supplier, so that action is taken at the appropriate time. These observations enable Walmart to react prior to issues getting out of hand, thus reducing loss and upholding public health (Redress Compliance, 2024).

In addition to that, dynamic pricing and demand forecasting are facilitated by AI application in the entire ecosystem. The application of AI allows processing huge amounts of data, from consumers' shopping patterns to checkout lanes, enabling Walmart to predict volatile demand and optimise inventories. This avoids overstocking or understocking, with little food wastage, which aligns with Walmart's sustainability objectives (IBM, 2023).

Blockchain is also crucial in the avoidance of contamination. Food recalls are both economically and reputationally costly. By utilising the IBM blockchain platform, Walmart is able to know exactly which lots have contaminated goods and remove only those rather than entire product lines. This not only limits economic loss but also avoids unnecessary consumer hysteria (Tan et al., 2018).

More importantly, IBM Food Trust enhances consumer trust. A blockchain ledger allows customers to monitor information regarding the source and processing of their food products through a QR code on the packaging. The buyer can see where the mango was grown, when it was harvested, and how it was transported, all in real-time and tamper-evident (Walmart Tech, 2022). This level of transparency is revolutionary in the context of global food safety concerns and supports an emerging demand for ethically sourced and traceable food.

The project also demonstrated the socioeconomic effect of AI and blockchain integration. Small farmers in emerging economies like China, where Walmart's pilot was initiated, were exposed to an open digital platform, thus improving their reputation and market access. AI-based solutions helped validate their processes, and blockchain helped provide downstream partners data integrity. Supply chain democratisation of this type is a move towards more inclusive and equitable global networks of trade (Tan et al., 2018).

Nevertheless, Walmart's quick digitalisation has its flip side. Perhaps the most worrying problem is the technical naivety of SMEs in the supply chain. Most of them either do not have infrastructure or even the knowledge to feed the right information to a blockchain-based platform. Added to this, even employing blockchain and AI technology is a costly venture at the start, particularly for SMEs operating on slim margins.

In response to these challenges, Walmart has focused on collaborative innovation. Rather than unilaterally imposing blockchain adoption, the company encourages partner collaboration through subsidies and training, as well as technical assistance. IBM Food Trust is designed to be scalable and user-friendly, which helps accelerate onboarding and ensure consistent data quality across the supply chain.

The solution also provides a large positive environmental impact. By the promotion of smart logistics and real-time tracking of goods, the IBM Food Trust reduces greenhouse gas emissions that result from duplicated transport and food waste.

In 2018, Walmart's board announced that thanks to IBM Food Trust and the other Walmart global initiatives to reduce its carbon footprint, the companies could have reached zero food waste for stores in the U.S., U.K., and Canada by 2025. Sadly, they failed to achieve their goal, but important steps forward have certainly been taken compared to the past.

In conclusion, the Walmart-IBM Food Trust collaboration exemplifies how AI and blockchain can revolutionise food supply chains through increased transparency, efficiency, and consumer trust. From the reduction in the response time to food sickness to empowering small-scale farmers and meeting sustainability objectives, this initiative sets a benchmark for future digital supply chain ecosystems. Even with current challenges, such as unsymmetrical scaling of the system, the Walmart case shows that digital food logistics innovation, via collaborative strategy and distributive design, is not only possible, but a prerequisite to global food security over the next several years.

4. The future of supply chain management

4.1 The incomplete revolution of SCM 4.0

In the previous paragraphs, individual technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), machine learning (ML), blockchain, cloud computing, and artificial intelligence (AI), collectively referred to as "Industry 4.0 technologies", were examined in detail. Until now, the focus was given to tracking individual contributions of each one of these innovations in the activities of the supply chain. In this paragraph, however, the perspective shifts from individual technologies to their collective influence.

Using the Industry 4.0 technologies, the traditional supply chain, long characterised by linearity and transactional nature, is undergoing a profound transformation into dynamic and interconnected ecosystems.

It is transforming value creation, delivery, and capture across sectors, enabling unprecedented levels of collaboration, efficiency, and resiliency possible.

The emergence of SCM 4.0 has a specific applicability to the broader agenda of digital transformation. As Oh and Park (2024) observe, the advent of digital technologies has altered the dependency of supply chain partners into more networked and multilateral linear relationships previously entertained by suppliers, manufacturers, and distributors. Companies today engage in more advanced webs of collaboration and competition spread out deeper in industry and geographical space. IoT and AI technology revolutionised information flows to enable real-time tracking of products, predictive demand forecasting, and dynamic planning of logistics.

In SCM 4.0, resilience emerged as the foundation of this new trend. Qader et al. (2022) state that businesses who were already implementing Industry 4.0 technologies before disruptive events like the COVID-19 pandemic were better positioned to withstand and adapt to crises. Supply chain openness has been empowered by technologies such as IoT and blockchain that allow organisations to detect disruption early, react suitably, and achieve continuity. Supply chain resilience has also improved through machine learning algorithms that allowed real-time dynamic decision-making. It helps companies to predict risk, implement changes in operations in real-time, and prevent disruption of product and information flow even if faced with uncertain circumstances.

However, the purpose of SCM 4.0 is not only to ensure the chances of being saved in the event of a disaster, as a lifebelt would do, but also and above all to maximise performance. Qader et al.'s (2022) research advocated a very strong positive relationship

between Industry 4.0 technology adoption and the improvement of supply chain performance. These kinds of technologies simplify integration, transparency, flexibility, and automating supply chain functions, thus cutting delivery time, minimising operational expense, providing quality assurance better, and enhancing customers' satisfaction.

Despite all of these, the SCM 4.0 times are still to arrive. Oh and Park (2024) add that while there are some industries, such as the automotive one, which have already begun the shift towards ecosystem-based models, others still maintain conventional supply chain organisations. While companies such as Hyundai Motors are constructing mobility ecosystems through the convergence of robotics and metaverse technology, many other sectors such as, for example, some segments in the electronics industry, still operate primarily in traditional supply chain frameworks. This heterogeneity emphasises the reality that this transition towards platform-based ecosystems is highly context-dependent as well as heterogeneous.

Moreover, digitalization has not only introduced opportunity but even posed more fundamental strategic challenges. As businesses become immersed in high-value ecosystems, competition increases not only among individual firms but also between networks of cooperating actors. For this reason, traditional industry boundaries collapse, and strategic imperatives emerge around cooperation, platform management, and innovation management. Oh and Park (2024) introduce the concept of "technological platforms" as a critical bridge between ecosystems and supply chains. These supply chain-based or ecosystem-based platforms enable collaboration, competition, and innovation among heterogeneous actors, who will represent the future value creator.

However, there remains a great deal of uncertainty as to what to do next. As Qader et al. (2022) note, while the advantages of adopting Industry 4.0 technologies are self-evident, the majority of organisations remain hesitant due to concerns about the possible extreme future sophistication in technology, cyberattacks, extremely high costs of implementation, and staff preparation. Supply chain managers will be forced to address the double challenge of utilising digital technology optimally and staying resilient and flexible in a volatile global environment. In addition, SCM 4.0's social and ethical dimensions, i.e., data privacy, algorithm transparency, and equal access to technology, are gaining attention, which will require new policy levers and governance institutions.

The future of SCM 4.0, therefore, is both promising and uncertain. New emerging AI, generative AI, blockchain, and IoT, however, are creating unprecedented opportunities for automation, optimization, and innovation in the entire value chain. Yet,

the pace of technological change, geopolitical risk, and environmental pressures add additional levels of complexity to be navigated by businesses with caution. As Oh and Park (2024) assert, success in the new world will depend not only on technology adoption but also on strategic vision, ecosystem awareness, and learning to navigate increasingly shifting patterns of cooperation and competition.

In conclusion, Supply Chain Management 4.0 represents a transformative shift that we are already living through. It is reshaping traditional supply chains into dynamic, responsive ecosystems powered by digital technologies. So much has been done, but so much more is yet to be achieved. Businesses need to embrace flexibility, resilience, and collaboration and enter into a future that is uncertain but promising. SCM 4.0 is not merely a destination but an evolving journey where innovation, strategic foresight, and ecosystem orchestration will determine who leads and who falls behind.

4.2 Sustainability in SCM: the rise of green and ethical supply chains

The early foundations of Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM), as observed in the research literature between 1999 and 2005, reveal a nascent yet determined effort to insert environmental concerns into traditional supply chain frameworks. At this time, GSCM was largely emerging as a response to increasing public pressure and evolving environmental regulation. Its conceptualisation, however, was very fragmented and exploratory. Researchers such as Beamon (1999) recognized the urgent environmental degradation driven by production systems and advocated the change of the linear supply chain system to a closed-loop system adopting end-of-life recovery, reuse, and recycling operations. This shift was only the first move towards sustainability, but at a general level, the environmental degradation entered the consciousness of many. This led to an emphasis on legal compliance and overall waste management rather than holistic environmental integration.

Sarkis (2003) built and proposed one of the earliest strategic choice models for green supply chains. His model acknowledged the growing complexity of choices in terms of environmental drivers, emphasizing the influence of the product life cycle, operation routines, and organisational routines on environmental performance. Using techniques such as the Analytic Network Process (ANP) emphasized the use of multi-criteria decision-making to achieve a balance in the environmental and business objectives trade-off. Notably, Sarkis emphasized the strategic importance of packaging,

reverse logistics, and supplier selection (e.g., ISO 14000-certified suppliers), all of which would be high-priority issues in today's GSCM. This complexity is shown in his analytical network model (see Figure 7), which highlights how different decision factors are connected in a green supply chain. However, the strategy was based on static models and did not incorporate dynamic sensitivity to market change or stakeholder engagement.

Figure 7: Functional model of an organizational supply chain with environmentally influential practices (adapted from Sarkis)

Source: Sarkis J. *Manufacturing strategy and environmental consciousness*. *Technovation* 1995;15(2):79–97.

Similarly, two years after always Sarkis with Hervani, Helms addressed the underdevelopment of performance measurement systems in GSCM due to the complexity of quantifying inter-organisational environmental effects owing to heterogeneity of measures and technological limitations. For this reason, they created a model that identified inputs such as regulatory pressure and internal cost drivers. However, also this time, the model had some deficiencies; in fact, it lacked substantial empirical support. At that stage, GSCM performance evaluation was more conceptual in nature as compared to being operational, with a stronger focus on a theoretical notion of sustainability without the sophisticated tools and systemic integration necessary for practical application.

The early literature shows that GSCM was still in its nascent phase, and it was typically limited to localised initiatives in individual companies or industrial clusters. Projects were more focused on environmental compliance, cost reduction, and risk reduction rather than long-term value creation and stakeholder-based sustainability. Concepts like industrial ecology and life cycle thinking were evoked but rarely systematically implemented. The specified roles should therefore be considered as a root but different from contemporary approaches, which now encompass sustainability across organisational planning, innovation, and cooperation networks.

As sustainability importance grew, the transition to Sustainable Supply Chain Management (SSCM) from Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM) was the signature of modern logistics and operations strategy.

While the early GSCM endeavours focused on environmental compliance and cost reduction, SSCM integrates the triple bottom line (TBL) philosophy (environmental, economic, and social dimensions) into supply chain activities. This broader definition signifies a paradigm shift whereby sustainability is not an add-on but a strategic driver that shapes supply chain configurations. Ahi and Searcy (2013) say that SSCM can be defined as “*the voluntary integration of sustainability into inter-organisational systems, enabling organisations to enhance performance and resilience while meeting stakeholder expectations*”. As evidenced by companies like IBM and Hewlett-Packard, sustainability has been integrated into fields like eco-design, energy efficiency, and sustainable sourcing (Rajeev et al., 2017).

Today, supply chain management is no longer limited to the coordination of production and logistics. It is a strategic end-to-end process that involves the sourcing of raw materials, procurement management, control of manufacturing, ensuring distribution, and customer satisfaction. In the last years, GEP, which is a global supply chain and procurement company, became known for providing advanced digital solutions and strategic consulting, by a market analysis have found that value creation, risk management, and sustainability have become focal points in modern supply chain practice. Modern SSCM is interested in circularity, ethical responsibility, and measurement of performance. Sustainable sourcing, reverse logistics, and life-cycle thinking are the new core pillars. In particular, companies increasingly utilise environmental performance indicators (e.g., carbon footprint, energy usage) and social performance indicators (e.g., labor conditions, societal contribution) to evaluate and develop their firm (Ali & Myvizhi, 2023).

The SSCM thus requires transparency, traceability, and stakeholder engagement at all phases of the supply chain.

However, with the growing supply network complexity at the global level comes the need to exploit the adoption of advanced digital tools capable of processing vast datasets and responding to rapidly changing variables. Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence are assuming central roles as drivers of SSCM innovation.

AI algorithms are utilised for predictive analytics, real-time decision-making, and anomaly detection to enable dynamic supply chain optimization under uncertainty. ML

algorithms learn through repeated exposure to data, allowing supply chains to react to demand variability, supplier risk, and compliance. These systems significantly influence demand forecasting, inventory management, and emissions monitoring. For instance, AI-driven routing algorithms minimize fuel consumption and delivery time by continually reshaping logistics plans based on traffic and weather conditions.

Alongside AI, metaheuristics are transforming how businesses approach SSCM optimization issues. These algorithms, such as Genetic Algorithms (GA), Ant Colony Optimization (ACO), Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), and Simulated Annealing, are high-level problem-solving algorithms designed to find near-optimal solutions for complex optimization problems that are too difficult to solve exactly (Abualigah et al., 2023).

Metaheuristics have the ability to efficiently search extensive solution spaces as well as identify Pareto-optimal trade-offs among competing objectives such as cost minimization, carbon footprint minimization, and social justice. For example, in supplier selection decision-making, they consider a number of factors, including price, lead time, environmental sustainability, and labour practices in generating well-balanced solutions (Rampantzi & Minis, 2017).

The use of these complex algorithms does not exclude the possibility of also employing linear programming models, but due to the SSCM complexity and dynamics, heuristic and metaheuristic algorithms are generally more appropriate (Abualigah et al., 2023). Certain models utilise fuzzy logic or stochastic programming to incorporate parameter uncertainty as volatility in demand or level of emissions.

Recent innovations include hybrid metaheuristic approaches, such as the combination of Whale Optimization Algorithm (WOA)⁸ and Variable Neighbourhood Search (VNS)⁹ algorithms for enhancing convergence rate and solution quality in green network design (Shokouhifar et al., 2023). Despite these developments, several challenges persist. High-quality real-time data remains difficult to obtain, especially in complex, multi-layered global supply chains. Algorithmic transparency and explainability are also required to facilitate the responsible use of AI in ethical decision-making applications. Companies

⁸ Whale Optimization Algorithm (WOA): It is an algorithm based on how humpback whales hunt in nature. It helps solve difficult problems by searching for good solutions in a smart and flexible way, often used in areas like supply chain planning.

⁹ Variable Neighbourhood Search (VNS): It is a method that looks for better solutions by changing the way it explores options. It avoids getting stuck in bad results and is useful for solving problems with many possible choices, like picking the best suppliers.

will have to invest more and more money to realise the full potential of AI and optimization technologies.

Overall, the SSCM evolution is a revolutionary transformation of supply chains. With the combined power of AI, ML, and metaheuristics, SSCM is now better able to balance environmental, economic, and social goals in real time. This combination of sustainability and advanced analytics positions supply chains not only as economic engines but also as drivers of ethical innovation and long-term sustainability.

4.3 Robotics in supply chain: automation and the future of logistics

The supply chain would naturally be aligned with the logistics and transport sector because the effective movement of products from suppliers to customers is solely dependent on the transport infrastructure and logistics management. Transport infrastructures facilitate the physical flow of products, while planning, execution, and control of the transport are conducted under logistics. The dependence assures that supply chains flow smoothly, meeting demand while maintaining service levels (Linbis Logistics Software, 2024).

The use of robots in transportation and logistics has enormous benefits in supply chain management. Robotic equipment, such as automated guided vehicles (AGVs) and autonomous mobile robots (AMRs), enhances the efficiency of operations through the performance of repetitive tasks like picking, packing, and sorting. Robotic automation reduces errors with manual handling, reduces processing time, and enhances the use of resources. For instance, Amazon's use of over 750000 robots has reduced order fulfilment costs by 25%, testifying to the revolutionary impact of robotics on operational effectiveness (Financial Times, 2025). In addition, robotics enables simpler control of inventory through tracking and processing real-time data, allowing better demand forecasting and stock management.

Robotic scalability offers supply chains the capability to respond instantly to customers' shifting demands, enhancing flexibility and responsiveness. Robots enhance job safety by performing risky or physically challenging tasks and make human labour free to respond to tasks on a higher scale (International Centre for Trade Transparency, 2024).

The growing adoption of robotics in transport and logistics not only amplifies operation but also redefines the foundational structures of the current modern supply chain. Autonomous robots, including both ground-based systems like AGVs and aerial

platforms such as drones, are becoming the leaders in a new generation of logistics where speed, accuracy, and agility are the measures of success. They are no longer experimental technologies but are seriously being contemplated as strategic tools to meet the evolving needs of international business (Wamba & Queiroz, 2022). Drones, in particular, have emerged as critical assets for last-mile delivery, particularly where there is no traditional infrastructure or in emergency scenarios where speed is essential. The capability of drones to defeat traffic congestion and deliver in difficult areas compresses delivery time and increases customers' satisfaction (Kaushik & Varghese, 2023).

Moreover, autonomous robots provide real-time data gathering and integration into systems that support dynamic decision-making along the supply chain. These technologies are typically sensor-attached and connected to Internet of Things (IoT) networks, creating real-time streams of running data that can be utilised to optimize performance. Through this web-based connectivity, supply chain managers will see more into products in transit, monitor weather and environmental factors, and respond to disruptions more proactively. Robotics platforms are not merely automating material handling; they are building intelligent, responsive, and adaptive logistics ecosystems.

One of the main reasons for incorporating robotics into logistics operations is the urgent requirement for supply chain continuity and adaptability, particularly in times of disruption like the COVID-19 pandemic. During the pandemic, robotic adoption mitigated manpower shortages without sacrificing throughput within warehouses and nodes of transport allowing to operate 24 hours a day in full compliance with healthcare protocols. (Kaushik & Varghese, 2023).

This experience confirmed the strategic value of robot automation as a way to ride out unexpected external shocks to resilience. For this reason after the pandemic, most companies increased investment in robotic technologies.

Robotic automation results in energy efficiency through the avoidance of redundant movement patterns and reduced standby time for transport equipment. Additionally, robots are also accuracy-based. This is because they are described to be defined by fewer errors, less wastage, and efficient packaging processes, and all these enhancements allow to make the supply chain more sustainable (Gondal et al., 2023).

On the workforce front, while the adoption of robots does displace certain manual roles, it also produces employment for upgrading and new employment in robot maintenance, system integration, and analysis. Rather than replacing human work, robotic integration is thus transforming work into higher-technology and added-value work.

Nevertheless, the successful deployment of robotics in transport and logistics depends on several critical factors. Organizational preparedness, technological infrastructure, and managerial support play pivotal roles in the adoption process.

Wamba and Queiroz (2022) argue that firms need to overcome barriers such as significant starting capital investment, computer security risks, and organizational opposition. These are all implications for change management and technological adoption strategy. Furthermore, companies must also look at interoperability between robot systems and their installed IT systems in a way that they are properly integrated and can easily exchange information along the supply chain.

In conclusion, robotic technologies in the transportation and logistics sector are transforming supply chain management. By enhancing operational efficiency, supporting real-time decision-making, and contributing to sustainability and resilience, robotic technologies are transforming delivery, warehousing, and goods transportation. While they continue to present deployment challenges, the overall value of robotics, from cost savings and service level enhancement to transforming labour puts them as critical enablers of the next-generation supply chain.

Conclusion

This thesis has been outlining Supply Chain Management (SCM) throughout its history, relevance, and profound influence of breakthrough technologies. The research initially elaborated SCM's role in making organizations successful, claiming that well-executed supply chain processes maximize customers' satisfaction and build competitive strengths.

Through a critical analysis of optimization technologies such as fuzzy logic, IoT-based technologies, blockchain technology for secure transactions, and integration with robotics/AI, the study emphasised how emerging technologies are reshaping the operations of the supply chain. The findings reveal a real and practical change in the scope of SCM during the decades. While traditional SCM was primarily focused on cost-saving and efficiency, with the emergence of new-generation high-tech technologies, it is now possible to choose smart, agile, and green supply chains. Notably, AI has emerged as a critical enabler of data-driven decision-making, improving demand forecasting, inventory control, and logistics optimization. Blockchain provided better traceability and transparency of supply chain networks, while IoT provided real-time tracking and automation. Green supply chain operations were also discussed with a specific reference to environmental and social stewardship.

However, the study also came across certain issues in embracing these technologies, including high implementation costs, data security concerns, and the need for employee training. These issues recognise the need for proper planning, ongoing improvement, and strong commitment at the organizational level to ensure that new technologies are implemented successfully.

Despite all these obstacles, the thesis demonstrated that the benefits of embracing new supply chain management technology outweigh its shortcomings. Empirical evidence suggests that organizations which managed these innovations are better positioned to achieve resilience, efficiency, and sustainability in an increasingly complex global market.

Based on the results of this thesis, future research will likely include the application of new technologies like 5G and quantum computing in supply chains. Surely AI decision making ethicality will raise concerns, and it will be a new field of study, particularly in critical decisions on SCM logistics.

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